

RISKS AND MITIGATIONS

2026-06-05

CIRPASS 2

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Version 1.1 (May 22, 2026)

Work package	WP Number
Task	4.1
Due Date	15/05/2026
Submission date	2026-06-05
Version	1.1
Deliverable lead	TNO
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Reviewers	Thijs Klooster (TNO)
Abstract	This document describes risks that can decrease the added value of the DPP system or might harm interest of parties. It proposes mitigations to those risks.
Keywords	System architecture, Digital product passports, ESPR, Risks, Mitigations
Citation	Roefs, D., van Nieuwenhuijze, H., Chawla, K., Smeets, N., Rongen, S., Kuiper, J., Rurup, R., Lazrak, M. N., & Bernier, C. (2025). Risks and mitigations: a companion to D4.1 Reference Architecture. CIRPASS-2 Consortium. D4.1 Reference Architecture. CIRPASS-2 Consortium. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15389456

Special thanks to Carsten Stöcker for his valuable input on risks related to authenticity and authorization.

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributor(s)
0.1	29/04/2025	Creation of the document a derivate form the Reference Architecture document	
1.0	12/05/2025	Finalizing document	
1.1	15/05/2026	Update this document based on changes to the Reference Architecture document version 1.1	

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48	Textile Exchange	TextileExchange	US
49	iPoint-Systems GmbH	iPoint	Germany

Grant Agreement No.: 101158775
 Call: DIGITAL-2023-CLOUD-DATA-04
 Topic: DIGITAL-2023-CLOUD-DATA-04-DIGIPASS
 Type of action: DIGITAL Simple Grants

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GLOSSARY

Entries marked with “” are based on their respective definition in Art. 2, ESPR.

‘Actor’ means a legal or natural person (e.g. John Doe, TNO) that fulfils a role¹. One actor can take on multiple roles.

‘Building Block’ is used as a synonym of ‘Application Service’, but also includes governance logic, and interoperable data functions used to enable DPP system capabilities.

‘Confidentiality’ means the property of ensuring that information is not made available or disclosed to unauthorized individuals, entities, or processes².

‘Data carrier’ “means a linear barcode symbol, a two-dimensional symbol or other automatic identification data capture medium that can be read by a device” (ESPR article 2(29))³

‘Delegated Act’ means a non-legislative act of general application. Delegated acts will supplement or amend parts of the ESPR, specifying, among others, obligations for economic operators, information requirements related to product aspects, requirements for specific product groups⁴.

‘Digital Product Passport’ (DPP) “means a set of data specific to a product that includes the information specified in the applicable delegated act, and that is accessible via electronic means through a data carrier” (Art. 2(28), ESPR).

‘Digital Product Passport Service Provider’ (DPPSP) “means a natural or legal person that is an independent third-party authorised by the economic operator which places the product on the market or puts it into service and that processes the digital product passport data for that product for the purpose of making such data available to economic operators and other relevant actors with a right to access those data under this Regulation or other Union law” (Art. 2(32), ESPR).

‘DPP system’ means a set of building blocks and the roles that deploy or perform these services, as required for the ESPR’s requirements for DPPs (e.g., ESPR Art. 9 and 10) and additionally optional building blocks.

‘DPP ecosystem’ means the complete set of actors and systems that create or use DPPs, and the interactions between these actors and systems.

‘Economic Operator’ “the manufacturer, the authorized representative, the importer, the distributor, the dealer and the fulfilment service provider” (Art. 2(46), ESPR).

‘End User’ means “any natural or legal person residing or established in the Union, to whom a product has been made available either as a consumer outside of any trade, business, craft or profession or as a professional end user in the course of its industrial or professional activities” (Art. 2(2), Market Surveillance Regulation (EU) 2019/1020, as cited by the ESPR Art. 2).

‘EU Registry’ means the DPP registry to be set up by the European Commission to store in a secure manner at least the unique identifiers linked to products placed on the market or put into service in the EU (ESPR Art. 13(1) and Recital 41).

‘Granularity level’ means the level at which DPPs are created, in accordance with the relevant delegated act. This can be at model, batch, or item level.

- **‘Model level’** means a version of a product of which all units share the same relevant characteristics, e.g., all units being produced within a set of designated factories.

¹ISO 23234:2021

²ISO/IEC TR 27550:2019

³It is understood that the data carrier itself may contain only the unique product identifier or a web link which enables locating the DPP data. Should the data carrier not contain a web link, it is understood that dedicated means will be defined to construct one (e.g., a professional application used exclusively in B2B contexts or a DPP link search portal).

⁴Delegated acts - EUR-Lex

- **'Batch level'** means a subset of a specific model composed of all items produced in a similar way, e.g., a group of products made in the same factory within a specific timeframe.
- **'Item level'** means a single unit of a model, e.g., an individual product.

'Data Integrity' means the ability to demonstrate that data in a DPP has not been altered, removed, or corrupted over time.

'Interoperability' means *"the ability of organizations to interact towards mutually beneficial goals, involving the sharing of information and knowledge between these organizations, through the business processes they support, by means of the exchange of data between their ICT systems"*⁵.

'Redirection service'⁶ means a building block that takes as an input a unique product identifier (or a weblink based a product identifier) and produces as output one or more 'active' weblinks that enable access to a (set of) other building block(s).

'responsible Economic Operator (rEO)' means an Economic Operator that has the legal obligation to create and/or to make available a DPP under ESPR Art. 9(2)(g), and all associated legal obligations.

'Role' means a set of tasks typically performed by one actor. (e.g. rEO, Independent Operator).

'Supply Chain Actor' means a legal person that performs an upstream activity or participates in a process of the product's value chain, up to the point where the product reaches the consumer.

'Unique product identifier' [‡] means *"a unique string of characters for the identification of a product that also enables a web link to the DPP"* (Art. 2(30), ESPR). The term 'enables' is understood to mean that, if needed, the unique product identifier can be used by a redirection service.

'User' means the actor which uses the DPP system to perform a task.

'Web portal' [‡] means the publicly accessible and user-friendly digital product passport web portal to be set up by the European Commission which guarantees stakeholders, such as customers, Economic Operators and other relevant actors, the ability to search for and compare data included in DPPs in a manner consistent with their respective access rights (ESPR Art. 14 and Recital 42).

⁵As defined in (European Commission, New European Interoperability Framework, https://ec.europa.eu/isa2/sites/default/files/eif_brochure_final.pdf (2017))

⁶In previous documents this was often referred to as a 'resolver'. As this term has a very specific meaning in certain contexts, this caused confusion. 'Redirection' more precisely covers the function required and aligns with [Options for redirection \(CIRPASS-2\)](#).

Abbreviation	Full Form
API	Application Programming Interface
B2B	Business-to-Business
DPP	Digital Product Passport
DPPSP	DPP Service Provider
DSSC	Data Spaces Support Centre
EC	European Commission
EO	Economic Operator
ESPR	Eco-design for Sustainable Products Regulation
IO	Independent Operator
rEO	responsible Economic Operator
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
UPI	Unique Product Identifier
VC	Verifiable Credential

1 INTRODUCTION

The DPP system brings a number of advantages to the European Union. For these advantages to materialize, it is essential that the DPP system⁷ continues to function correctly, including in the face of actors that behave in a non-compliant manner or with malicious intent. This document presents an aggregation of risks that could undermine the DPP system and describes mitigations intended to make the system more resilient to the effects of those risks. These mitigations have been considered in the design of the CIRPASS-2 Reference Architecture⁸. Risks that could not be mitigated are listed in the final chapter of this document.

1.1 SCOPE OF THE ANALYSIS

The scope of this analysis includes both the technical and non-technical aspects of the DPP system. Both are analyzed because there is overlap between them: non-technical risks can sometimes be addressed through technical solutions, and technical risks can sometimes be addressed through non-technical means. It has been found that many risks of abuse of the system cannot feasibly be mitigated using technical means alone and therefore require non-technical mitigation measures.

1.2 ACTORS THAT MIGHT BEHAVE WITH MALICIOUS INTENT

Various types of actors interact with the DPP system. As different actors have different capabilities and interests, each actor must be considered separately. The following actors have been considered capable of behaving in a non-compliant or malicious manner that can harm the functioning of the DPP system:

- responsible Economic Operator (rEO)
- Independent Operator (IO)
- Digital Product Passport Service Provider (DPPSP)
- Supply chain actors
- End users
- State actors
- Criminal groups
- Hacktivists
- Insider threats

For the following actors, malicious intent is assumed to arise only from insider threats (i.e. it is assumed that no government body has the goal of harming the functioning of the DPP system):

- The European Commission (EC)
- Other government bodies

⁷This includes both the technical and non-technical components.

⁸[D4.1 Reference Architecture](#)

2 RISKS

In this chapter, first a definition of risks is given in Section 2.1. Then, the process of identifying relevant risks is explained in Section 2.2. A list of all identified events that underlie risks is presented in Section 2.3.

2.1 DEFINITION

The DPP system is intended to bring more benefits than costs⁹. Some costs of the DPP system are not fixed: those costs might be incurred only as the result of an action¹⁰ performed by an actor while the DPP system is operational. Such a cost that might be incurred is what is meant by a 'risk' in this document.

2.2 IDENTIFYING RISKS

Risks come into existence because:

1. a *situation* can exist in which a cost is incurred;
2. that situation can come to exist due to an *action* by an actor; and
3. that actor is *motivated* to perform the action.

2.2.1 METHODOLOGY OF IDENTIFYING RISKS

To identify risks for the DPP system, three methods have been used:

1. Identifying events, then actions, then motivations;
2. Identifying motivations, then actions, then events;
3. Identifying actions, then events and motivations.

METHOD 1

Events that can arise due to the introduction of the DPP system, and that incur a cost, are identified. Then, all actions that can cause such an event are identified. Finally, the actions are filtered to retain only those for which at least one actor could be motivated to perform the action. In the context of risk, only events that incur a cost are considered. Therefore, for every event, two questions need to be answered before it is identified as a risk:

1. Can this event be caused by an action?
2. What is the motivation of an actor to cause this event?

METHOD 2

Motivations of actors are identified first, followed by the question of which actions the actor can take as a result of that motivation, which situations may arise from those actions, and whether those situations incur a cost.

⁹Benefits and costs are not necessarily monetary, but may also include social, strategic, and environmental gains and losses.

¹⁰The terms 'action' and 'motivation' should be interpreted broadly. They also include inaction caused by a lack of motivation, as such inaction can also result in an event (e.g. the inclusion of a part containing dangerous substances in a product that is not included in the DPP).

METHOD 3

Actions that can be performed by actors are identified first, followed by the question of whether the action causes an event that incurs a cost and whether the actor that can perform the action is motivated to do so.

2.2.2 ACTORS

Different types of actors can be identified, each with different motivations and capabilities. A risk is only relevant if an actor has both the motivation and the capability to perform the action¹¹.

For every event, relevant actions have been aggregated. The aggregated events and actions are presented in Section 2.3. Actions are listed only if a motivation could be identified for at least one actor to perform the action. Motivations themselves are not included to improve the readability of the document.

2.3 LIST OF ACTIONS

The list of actions below is structured based on events, with relevant actions listed under each event. Events are aligned to the left of the page, with related actions indented one level below the events. Motivations are omitted for readability.

Actions are labeled as non-technical (👤) or technical (⚙️) actions. Non-technical actions arise from malicious use of the system or from bypassing the system. Such actions can be performed even when the system operates exactly as intended¹². Technical actions are performed by exploiting a technical flaw in the system or its design and can occur only when the system does not operate exactly as intended. Almost all identified actions undermine the goals of the DPP system (e.g. enabling access to accurate product information), while only a few actions directly damage the technical system itself.

Events are categorized according to the life cycle of a DPP: creation, storage, retrieval, updating, and deletion.

EVENTS OCCURRING DURING THE CREATION OF THE DPP OR PRODUCT

- A new DPP containing incorrect information is added to the system
 - 1A. 👤 The rEO provides too little information
 - 2A. 👤 The rEO provides too much information
 - 3A. 👤 The rEO provides incorrect information
- An existing DPP is used for a new product
 - 4A. 👤 The rEO reuses one of its own DPPs for a product
 - 5A. 👤 The rEO uses a DPP of another rEO for a product
- A new DPP for a non-existing product is submitted to the system
 - 6A. 👤⚙️ A (fake) rEO submits a DPP with bogus information
 - 7A. ⚙️ The rEO submits an excessive number of DPPs to perform a denial-of-service attack
- A new product is made but no DPP is submitted
 - 8A. 👤 The rEO creates a new product but does not create a new DPP

¹¹For example, a consumer might be motivated to add a new, expensive part to the DPP of a product that does not actually have that part in order to increase the product's value. However, an average consumer typically lacks the technical knowledge required to compromise the digital systems of an rEO. A state actor might have the capability to compromise such systems, but is unlikely to be motivated to do so for this purpose. As long as no actor is both motivated and capable, the risk remains limited.

¹²For example, a malicious state actor identifies a crucial producer in a strategic supply chain by requesting a DPP.

- A DPP that is being created is intercepted during transfer
 - 9A. ⚙️ An actor intercepts the information submitted during creation

EVENTS OCCURRING DURING THE STORAGE OF THE DPP OR PRODUCT

- A DPP can no longer be retrieved
 - 10A. 👤 The DPP host deletes the information
 - 11A. ⚙️ The DPP host stops operating
 - 12A. ⚙️ An actor performs a cyber-attack on the DPP host, causing DPPs to be lost
- The information in a DPP is altered with malicious intent
 - 13A. 👤 The DPP host alters the information
 - 14A. ⚙️ An actor performs a cyber-attack on the DPP host that alters DPP information
- A product is altered such that it links to a different DPP
 - 15A. 👤 The physical DPP data carrier is modified, replaced, or hidden while a new link pointing to a different DPP is attached
 - 16A. 👤 The physical DPP data carrier is modified, replaced, or hidden while a new link pointing to a malicious web page is attached
- Confidential information in a DPP is accessed by unauthorized parties
 - 17A. 👤 The DPP host accesses information it should not access
 - 18A. ⚙️ A cyber-attack targets the DPP host with the objective of stealing DPP information
 - 19A. 👤 A malicious actor pretends to have the right to access information
 - 20A. 👤 A malicious actor pays an authorized party to access and share confidential information

EVENTS OCCURRING DURING THE RETRIEVAL OF THE DPP

- The physical DPP data carrier becomes unreadable or is lost
 - 21A. ⚙️ An actor with physical access to the product makes the data carrier unusable
 - 22A. 👤 The rEO attaches a low-quality data carrier that degrades over time or through rough usage
 - 23A. 👤⚙️ A handler of the product destroys the data carrier
- The redirection service is no longer able to resolve the DPP identifier
 - 24A. ⚙️ The redirection service provider stops providing the service
 - 25A. ⚙️ A denial-of-service attack targets the redirection service
- Due to a storage-related issue, the DPP can no longer be retrieved (see 'Storage of the DPP or product')
- A DPP that is being retrieved is intercepted during transfer
 - 26A. ⚙️ An actor intercepts the information
 - 27A. ⚙️ An actor intercepts and modifies the information

- 28A. ⚙️ An actor performs a man-in-the-middle attack, acting as both DPP host and requester
- Retrieval of DPPs is monitored
 - 29A. ⚙️ An actor monitors internet traffic
 - 30A. ⚙️ An actor identifies end users retrieving a DPP
- Actors aggregate public DPP information for malicious purposes
 - 31A. 👤 Actors compile an overview of supply chain dependencies
 - 32A. 👤 Actors compile an overview of product properties used in sensitive equipment
 - 33A. 👤 Actors use DPP dependency information to conduct automated spear-phishing attacks
 - 34A. 👤 Actors compile an overview of strategic products a country can produce to assess strategic autonomy

EVENTS OCCURRING DURING THE UPDATING OF THE DPP OR PRODUCT

- A DPP is updated while the product is not
 - 35A. 👤 The rEO updates the DPP with incorrect information
 - 36A. 👤 An authorized actor updates the DPP with incorrect information
 - 37A. 👤 An authorized actor updates the DPP so frequently that it becomes difficult to load or view
 - 38A. 👤 An unauthorized actor pretends to have update rights and updates the DPP incorrectly
 - 39A. ⚙️ Incorrect updates are made after a successful cyber-attack on an authorized actor
- A product is updated while the DPP is not
 - 40A. 👤 An IO updates the product but neglects to update the DPP
 - 41A. 👤 An end user alters the product but does not update the DPP
 - 42A. 👤 A malicious third party alters the product without updating the DPP
- Both product and DPP are updated, but the DPP does not accurately reflect the product
 - 43A. 👤 An IO updates the product but updates the DPP inaccurately
 - 44A. 👤 An end user updates the product but updates the DPP inaccurately
 - 45A. 👤 A malicious third party updates both product and DPP inaccurately

EVENTS OCCURRING DURING THE DELETION OF THE DPP OR PRODUCT

- The DPP is destroyed while the product is not
 - 46A. 👤 A recycler reports the product as destroyed while it is not
 - 47A. 👤 An end user falsely reports destruction of the product
 - 48A. 👤 The DPP host destroys the DPP while the product has not been recycled
 - 49A. 👤 An actor falsely presents itself as a recycler and reports destruction
- The product is destroyed while the DPP is not
 - 50A. 👤 A recycler does not notify the DPP host of destruction

- 51A. The product is lost (e.g. fire, flood) and the owner does not notify the DPP host
- 52A. The product is brought to a landfill without the DPP being destroyed

3 MITIGATIONS

This chapter presents mitigations to the risks listed in the previous chapter. Mitigations are measures that can be taken to lower a risk. Some risks can be completely eliminated. Other risks are only reduced, either because a mitigation lowers the cost that might be incurred or because the mitigation itself introduces a new risk. If such a new risk is identified, an additional mitigation can be considered.

3.1 METHODOLOGY

In Chapter 2, it is argued that a risk comes into existence because a *situation* can arise in which a *motivated* actor can perform an *action*. If either the situation, the action, or the motivation is partially or completely removed, the risk is reduced. Therefore, ways to prevent situations from arising, to make actions impossible, or to remove motivations have been investigated in order to identify suitable mitigations.

3.2 SCOPE

All considered mitigations are listed in this chapter. This includes both mitigations that have been included in the reference architecture and mitigations that have not been included. It also includes non-technical mitigations, which cannot be included in the reference architecture.

3.3 STRUCTURE

The risks of Chapter 2 are repeated here, aligned to the left of the page, with the same risk numbers that are used in Chapter 2. Each risk is followed by one or more possible mitigations, which are indented one level. As discussed, mitigations may themselves introduce new risks. If such a risk has been identified, it is placed below the mitigation and indented one level further. This nesting may be repeated. Some risks are not followed by a mitigation; in those cases, no suitable mitigation has been identified.

EVENTS OCCURRING DURING THE CREATION OF THE DPP OR PRODUCT

- **1A. Risk: The rEO provides too little information**
 - Possible mitigation: A service validates whether all required fields are submitted.
 - * Risk: The rEO submits all required fields but provides too little information within them.
 - Possible mitigation: The rEO is penalized for providing insufficient information.
- **2A. Risk: The rEO provides too much information**
 - Possible mitigation: See mitigations for Risk 1A.
 - Possible mitigation: The API allows querying only specific sections of a DPP (e.g. only mandatory information). This allows retrieval even if the DPP has become difficult to download due to malicious inflation of its size.
- **3A. Risk: The rEO provides incorrect information**
 - Possible mitigation: See mitigations for Risk 1A.
 - Possible mitigation: The rEO is penalized.
 - * Risk: The rEO claims it was unclear that more information had to be provided.

- Possible mitigation: The rEO is penalized nonetheless.
- * Risk: The rEO claims information received from other parties was incorrect.
 - Possible mitigation: The rEO is penalized nonetheless.
- **4A. Risk: The rEO reuses one of its own DPPs for another product**
 - Possible mitigation: The rEO is penalized for reusing a DPP.
 - * Risk: The rEO accepts the risk and proceeds anyway.
- **5A. Risk: The rEO uses a DPP of another rEO for a product**
 - Possible mitigation: The rEO is penalized for reusing a DPP.
 - * Risk: The rEO accepts the risk and proceeds anyway.
- **6A. Risk: The rEO submits a DPP with bogus information**
 - Possible mitigation 1: Only authenticated and authorized rEOs can submit DPPs.
 - Possible mitigation 2: rEOs can be temporarily or permanently denied the ability to submit DPPs.
 - Possible mitigation 3: Submitted DPPs can be altered, removed, or partially hidden by a trusted administrator.
 - Possible mitigation 4: Submitted DPPs can be superseded by a new DPP submitted by the rEO.
 - * Risk: The rEO does not comply.
 - Possible mitigation: The rEO's status as a trusted party is revoked.
- **7A. Risk: The rEO submits an excessive number of DPPs as part of a denial-of-service attack**
 - Possible mitigation 1: Rate limiting is applied to limit the number of DPPs submitted by an rEO.
 - Possible mitigation 2: The rEO loses the right to submit DPPs after exceeding allowed thresholds.
- **8A. Risk: The rEO creates a new product but does not create a DPP**
 - Possible mitigation: The rEO is penalized for failing to create a DPP for a new product.

EVENTS OCCURRING DURING THE STORAGE OF THE DPP OR PRODUCT

- **10A. Risk: The DPP host deletes the information**
 - Possible mitigation 1: A DPP host cannot be the rEO, which may have an interest in deleting the information.
 - Possible mitigation 2: A backup is kept by a third party that cannot be altered or removed by the rEO.
 - * Risk: The third party is dependent on the rEO (e.g. as a customer) and can be pressured to alter or remove the DPP.
 - Possible mitigation: The backup-holding party must be independent from the rEO.
 - Possible mitigation 3: DPPs are cryptographically signed by the rEO so that holders of copies can prove authenticity.

- **11A. Risk: The DPP host stops operating**
 - Possible mitigation: A third party keeps a backup.
 - * Risk: The third party also stops operating after some time.
 - Possible mitigation: The backup must be duplicated with an additional independent party if the rEO stops operating.
- **12A. Risk: An actor performs a cyber-attack on the DPP host causing DPPs to be lost**
 - Possible mitigation: A third party maintains a backup.
- **13A. Risk: The DPP host alters the information**
 - Possible mitigation 1: The DPP host cannot be the rEO, who might have an interest in altering the information.
 - Possible mitigation 2: A backup is kept by another party and alterations are logged.
 - * Risk: The other party is dependent on the rEO (e.g. because the rEO is the customer).
 - Possible mitigation: The other party must be independent from the rEO.
 - Possible mitigation 3: The rEO cryptographically signs the DPP so that unauthorized modifications can be detected and the rEO cannot deny having created the original DPP.
 - * Risk: The rEO accepts the risk that the faulty DPP is not retained, preventing a victim from proving modification.
 - Possible mitigation: Modifying DPPs is penalized more severely, as intent can be proven when a victim has a copy of the signed DPP.
 - * Risk: The rEO creates and cryptographically signs multiple DPPs and selectively shares altered versions.
 - Possible mitigation: This type of fraud is penalized more severely and can be proven if a victim has a copy of the altered, signed DPP.
- **14A. Risk: An actor performs a cyber-attack on the DPP host that alters DPP information**
 - Possible mitigation: A third party maintains a backup.
 - * Risk: Alterations are made in a way that is difficult to detect.
 - Possible mitigation: The backup provider regularly verifies the correctness of the DPP.
 - Possible mitigation: DPPs are cryptographically signed, and the signing process is protected against cyber-attacks. An attacker that modifies a DPP cannot sign the altered data.
 - * Risk: A highly advanced actor also compromises the signing system.
- **15A. Risk: The physical DPP data carrier is modified, replaced, or hidden while a new link pointing to a different DPP is attached**
 - Possible mitigation 1: A backup data carrier is attached to the product.
 - * Risk: If an end user can identify the backup data carrier, so can a malicious actor.
 - Possible mitigation 1: The purchase agreement lists the original DPP or UID.
 - Possible mitigation 2: National inspections focus on product categories prone to carrier replacement.

- Possible mitigation 3: A DPP application visually verifies the product together with the data carrier.
- Possible mitigation 2: All DPP links are routed through a central component. End users are informed that only such links provided by the central component are trustworthy.
- **16A. Risk: The physical DPP data carrier is modified, replaced, or hidden while a new link pointing to a malicious web page is attached**
 - Possible mitigation 1: Applications reading data carriers verify that links point to known and valid DPP URLs.
 - Possible mitigation 2: A backup data carrier is attached to the product.
 - * Risk: If an end user can identify the backup data carrier, so can a malicious actor.
 - Possible mitigation: Users are instructed to verify the destination of DPP links.
 - Possible mitigation 3: All DPP links are routed through a central component. End users are informed that only links that go through the central component can be trusted.
- **17A. Risk: The DPP host accesses information it should not access**
 - Possible mitigation 1: The DPP host never stores or receives information it is not required to access.
 - Possible mitigation 2: Sensitive data is encrypted with keys unknown to the DPP host.
- **18A. Risk: A cyber-attack targets the DPP host to steal DPP information**
 - Possible mitigation 1: Sensitive information is not stored directly in the DPP; instead, verifiable proofs are provided that prove the information is present and not modifiable anymore.
 - Possible mitigation 2: The DPP host applies cybersecurity measures proportional to data sensitivity.
 - * Risk: The costs of such security measures become excessive.
- **19A. Risk: A malicious actor pretends to have the right to access information**
 - Possible mitigation: Only authenticated and authorized parties with correct roles can access information.
 - * Risk: Credentials are stolen or brute-forced.
 - Possible mitigation: Credentials can be revoked.
 - * Risk: Parties receive authorizations they should not have.
- **20A. Risk: A malicious actor pays an authorized party to access and share confidential information**
 - Possible mitigation 1: Authorizations are scoped minimally.
 - Possible mitigation 2: Access to confidential information is logged.
 - Possible mitigation 3: Actors must justify the need for access.
 - Possible mitigation 4: Data is categorized rather than disclosed in full (e.g. metal content > 50% or < 50%).
 - Possible mitigation 5: Access to information without legitimate purpose is penalized.
 - * Risk: An actor with legitimate access also sells data to malicious third parties.

EVENTS OCCURRING DURING THE RETRIEVAL OF THE DPP

- **21A. Risk: An actor with physical access to the product makes the data carrier unusable**
 - Possible mitigation 1: The purchase agreement contains the product identifier or data carrier information that enables access to the DPP.
 - Possible mitigation 2: A web portal exists that allows identification of a product without the data carrier.
- **22A. Risk: The rEO adds a low-quality data carrier that becomes unusable over time or through rough use**
 - Possible mitigation: Mandatory robustness requirements are defined for data carriers.
- **23A. Risk: Someone handling the product destroys the data carrier**
 - Possible mitigation 1: Products without a DPP are not permitted, and replacing a data carrier is costly, discouraging deliberate destruction.
 - Possible mitigation 2: Mandatory robustness requirements are defined for data carriers.
 - * Risk: This only prevents accidental destruction.
 - Possible mitigation 1: The purchase agreement includes the product identifier or data carrier reference.
 - Possible mitigation 2: A web portal allows identification of the product without a data carrier.
- **24A. Risk: The redirection service provider stops providing the redirection service**
 - Possible mitigation: Another party can take over the redirection function when the original provider stops operating.
- **25A. Risk: A denial-of-service attack is performed on the DPP identification process**
 - Possible mitigation: The redirection service provider implements adequate protections to maintain availability during DDoS attacks.
- **26A. Risk: An actor intercepts DPP information during retrieval**
 - Possible mitigation: DPPs are transmitted over properly encrypted connections.
- **27A. Risk: An actor intercepts and modifies DPP information during retrieval**
 - Possible mitigation: DPPs are transmitted over properly encrypted connections.
- **28A. Risk: An actor performs a man-in-the-middle attack, impersonating both DPP host and requester**
 - Possible mitigation: DPP hosts and DPP requesters mutually authenticate.
- **29A. Risk: An actor monitors internet traffic related to DPP retrieval**
 - Possible mitigation 1: DPPs are hosted in a centralized manner.
 - Possible mitigation 2: Mixer or proxy hosts aggregate multiple DPP requests on behalf of many users, reducing traceability.
 - Possible mitigation 3: Unauthorized monitoring of internet traffic within the European Union is prevented.

- **30A. Risk: An actor identifies end users when retrieving a DPP (end-user tracking)**
 - Possible mitigation: It is mandated that web pages displaying DPPs do not contain JavaScript or tracking technologies.
 - * Risk: Actors employ server-side tracking mechanisms.
 - Possible mitigation: Such behavior is penalized.
 - * Risk: Malicious actors (possibly outside the EU continue) tracking activities.
- **31A. Risk: Actors compile an overview of supply chain dependencies**
 - Possible mitigation 1: A decentralized rate-limiting mechanism is implemented (feasibility uncertain).
 - * Risk: Determined actors circumvent rate limiting.
 - Possible mitigation 2: Batch and item level DPPs are not indexed
 - * Risk: The actors guess or try all possible locations of the DPPs and access them directly
 - Possible mitigation: Locations of the batch level and item level DPPs are randomly taken from a large high entropy space
 - Possible mitigation 3: DPPs of sensitive products or production facilities are not publicly available
- **32A. Risk: Actors compile an overview of properties of products that are likely to be used in sensitive equipment**
 - Possible mitigation 1: A decentralized monitoring and detection system is implemented (feasibility uncertain) that identifies actors who appear to be compiling such overviews and blocks their access.
 - Possible mitigation 2: DPPs of sensitive products or production facilities are not publicly available
- **33A. Risk: Actors use information from DPP dependencies to perform automated spear-phishing attacks**
 - Possible mitigation 1: Product ownership information is not included in a DPP unless explicit consent is given.
 - Possible mitigation 2: Locations of the batch level and item level DPPs are randomly taken from a large high entropy space
- **34A. Risk: Actors compile an overview of strategic products a country can produce to assess strategic autonomy**
 - Possible mitigation: See mitigations for Risk 32A

EVENTS OCCURRING DURING THE UPDATING OF THE DPP OR PRODUCT

- **35A. Risk: The rEO updates the DPP with incorrect information**
 - Possible mitigation 1: The previous version of the DPP is retained, and a log records what was updated, by whom, and when. This log is not maintained by the rEO.
 - Possible mitigation 2: Providing incorrect updates is penalized.
- **36A. Risk: An actor with the right to update the DPP updates it with incorrect information**
 - Possible mitigation 1: Only authenticated and authorized actors can update the DPP.

- Possible mitigation 2: The set of authorized actors is kept as small as possible.
- Possible mitigation 3: Every update is logged, including what was changed, when, and possibly why.
- Possible mitigation 4: Updates are cryptographically signed so that actors cannot deny having submitted incorrect information.
- **37A. Risk: An authorized actor updates the DPP so frequently that it becomes difficult to load or view due to the size of the change set**
 - Possible mitigation: It is possible to request only the latest version of the DPP, without the full change history.
- **38A. Risk: An actor pretends to have the right to update the DPP and submits incorrect information**
 - Possible mitigation: Only authenticated and authorized actors can update a DPP.
 - * Risk: Authorizations are over-scoped or outdated.
 - Possible mitigation: Define fine-grained roles with limited validity periods.
 - * Risk: Credential revocations are not checked frequently enough.
 - Possible mitigation: Credential validity is verified whenever possible.
 - * Risk: Credentials are replayed by an actor impersonating another party.
 - * Risk: A credential-issuing authority is compromised.
 - Possible mitigation: Issuing authorities can also be revoked.
 - * Risk: An actor establishes a business within the EU, impersonates a legitimate company, and updates the DPP.
 - Possible mitigation: This behavior is penalized. **Risk: The actor operates from a different jurisdiction.**
- **39A. Risk: An actor successfully compromises an authorized updater and submits incorrect DPP updates**
 - Possible mitigation 1: Actors can review all updates made to DPPs using their accounts.
 - Possible mitigation 2: Authorized actors implement appropriate security measures to protect credentials.
 - Possible mitigation 3: An anomaly-detection system identifies suspicious update behavior.
 - Possible mitigation 4: Updates are cryptographically signed, and signing systems are more secure as they are a smaller, independent system.
 - * Risk: A highly advanced actor also compromises the signing system.
- **40A. Risk: An IO updates the product but neglects to update the DPP**
 - Possible mitigation: This behavior is penalized.
- **41A. Risk: An end user alters the product but does not update the DPP**
 - No suitable mitigation has been identified.

- **42A. Risk: A malicious third party alters the product but does not update the DPP**
 - Possible mitigation 1: This behavior is penalized.
 - Possible mitigation 2: Physical security measures prevent unauthorized product alteration.
- **43A. Risk: An IO updates the product but updates the DPP inaccurately**
 - Possible mitigation: This behavior is penalized.
- **44A. Risk: An end user updates the product but updates the DPP inaccurately**
 - No suitable mitigation has been identified.
- **45A. Risk: A malicious third party updates the product and updates the DPP inaccurately**
 - Possible mitigation 1: This behavior is penalized.
 - Possible mitigation 2: Physical security measures are implemented to prevent such alterations.

EVENTS OCCURRING DURING THE DELETION OF THE DPP OR PRODUCT

- **46A. Risk: A recycler reports that a product is destroyed when it is not, and the DPP host destroys the DPP**
 - Possible mitigation: This behavior is penalized.
 - * Risk: Once the DPP is destroyed, it is difficult to prove wrongdoing.
 - Possible mitigation: The DPP is not deleted; instead, a “destroyed” status label is applied.
 - Risk: The recycler denies submitting the destruction report.
 - * Possible mitigation: Destruction reports must be cryptographically signed by the recycler.
- **47A. Risk: An end user reports that a product is destroyed when it is not, and the DPP host destroys the DPP**
 - Possible mitigation: This behavior is penalized.
 - * Risk: Once the DPP is destroyed, it is difficult to prove wrongdoing.
 - Possible mitigation: The DPP is not deleted; instead, a “destroyed” status label is applied.
 - Risk: The end user denies submitting the destruction report.
- **48A. Risk: The DPP host destroys the DPP, claiming it has been recycled, while the product has not been recycled**
 - Possible mitigation: This behavior is penalized.
- **49A. Risk: An actor pretends to be a recycler and reports the product as destroyed**
 - Possible mitigation 1: Only authenticated and authorized actors with the correct roles can report destruction.
 - Possible mitigation 2: This behavior is penalized.
 - * Risk: Once the DPP is destroyed, it is difficult to prove wrongdoing.
 - Possible mitigation: The DPP is not deleted; instead, a “destroyed” status label is applied.

- **50A. Risk: A recycler does not notify the DPP host that a product has been destroyed**
 - Possible mitigation: This behavior is penalized.
 - * Risk: If no physical trace of the product exists, it may be difficult to prove the product was recycled.
- **51A. Risk: A product is lost (e.g. due to fire or flooding), and the owner does not notify the DPP host**
 - No suitable mitigation has been identified.
- **52A. Risk: A product is brought to a landfill but the DPP is not destroyed**
 - Possible mitigation: Products are automatically marked as deleted after a predefined period.

4 RISKS THAT ARE NOT HANDLED

The reference architecture aims to minimize risks. Most risks are addressed through measures included in the reference architecture. However, some risks are not handled. Risks are not handled either because no suitable mitigation exists or because mitigation is deemed too costly, either financially or in terms of system burden. If a risk is considered significant but is not mitigated in the reference architecture or otherwise, it is included in the table below.

It should be noted that this section assumes that all recommendations in the reference architecture are implemented, and that all parties, including less digitally advanced Economic Operators, sign DPPs using JOSE proofs. System components that do not implement all recommendations or do not sign DPPs will face additional unhandled risks.

The table below lists, in the second column, the action that constitutes the unmitigated risk. In the third column, a description of the impact of the risk is provided.

Table 2: RISKS THAT ARE NOT HANDLED

#	Action	Risk
5A	The rEO uses a DPP of another rEO for a product	Products are linked to a DPP that does not accurately describe the product, which diminishes trust in the DPP system and undermines its effectiveness
15A	The physical DPP data carrier is modified, replaced, or hidden while a new link pointing to a different DPP is attached to the product	Products are linked to a DPP that does not accurately describe the product, which diminishes trust in the DPP system and undermines its effectiveness
16A	The physical DPP data carrier is modified, replaced, or hidden while a new link pointing to a malicious web page is attached to the product	End-user devices and systems may become compromised
18A	A cyber-attack targets the DPP host with the objective of stealing DPP information	Intellectual property is stolen, diminishing company profitability and potentially undermining the strategic position of the European economy
20A	A malicious actor pays an authorized party to access and share confidential information	Intellectual property is stolen, diminishing company profitability and potentially undermining the strategic position of the European economy
21A	An actor with physical access to the product makes the data carrier unusable	The added value of the DPP system is reduced
30A	An actor identifies end users when retrieving a DPP	The privacy of end users is violated
31A	Actors compile an overview of supply chain dependencies	Strategic information about production within the European Union becomes available to strategic competitors
32A	Actors compile an overview of properties of products that are likely to be used in sensitive equipment	Adversarial actors can conduct more targeted attacks against sensitive equipment

34A	Actors compile an overview of strategic products a country can produce to assess strategic autonomy	Strategic information about production capabilities within the European Union becomes available to strategic competitors
41A	An end user alters the product but does not update the DPP	Trust in the DPP system diminishes, and products may be incorrectly valued or recycled improperly
43A	An end user updates the product but updates the DPP inaccurately	Trust in the DPP system diminishes, and products may be incorrectly valued or recycled improperly
44A	An end user updates the product but updates the DPP inaccurately	End users inaccurately update DPPs due to lack of qualification or malicious intent, leading to reduced trust in DPPs for second-hand products